

PALEO-LAYERED STRUCTURES REVEALED AT THE VON KÁRMÁN CRATER USING LUNAR PENETRATING RADAR. Y. Xu¹, X. Meng¹, L. Zhang², H. Cao³, J. Li³, Y. Qian⁴, L. Lai⁵, ¹ State Key Laboratory of Lunar and Planetary Sciences, Macau University of Science and Technology, Macau (yixu@must.edu.mo), ² School of Earth Science and Engineering, Sun Yat-sen University, Guangzhou, China, ³ Key Laboratory of Applied Geophysics, College of Geo-Exploration Science and Technology, Jilin University, Changchun, China, ⁴Department of Earth Sciences and Laboratory for Space Research, The University of Hong Kong, Hong Kong, ⁵School of Science, Jiangxi University of Science and Technology, Ganzhou, China

Introduction: On January 3, 2019, the Chang'e-4 lunar probe successfully landed in the South Pole-Aitken Basin (SPA) (Fig. 1a), achieving the first-ever soft landing on the far side of the Moon [1]. The landing site is within the Von Kármán Crater (186 kilometers in diameter), situated at the center of the SPA (Fig. 1b). The terrain of the landing area is relatively flat, with surface undulations within a range of approximately 60 meters.

Lunar Penetrating Radar (LPR) is one of the key scientific payloads onboard the Chang'e-4 lunar rover, Yutu-2. It operates at two frequency channels (60 MHz and 500 MHz) with vertical resolutions of 10 m and 0.3 m, and detection depths of 500 m and 50 m, respectively [2]. This instrument provides a unique opportunity to reveal the stratified structure and estimate the material composition of the lunar subsurface at depths of several hundred meters.

Data and Method: Since its landing, the Yutu-2 lunar rover has traversed over 1,400 m, collecting scientific data over 62 lunar days. The path of the Yutu-2 rover is shown in Figure 1b. We first preprocessed the LPR data by removing duplicate traces, applying gain, band-pass filtering, trace spacing equalization, and least squares Kirchhoff migration. The preprocessed data were used for wave impedance inversion to estimate permittivity and peak frequency calculations to determine the loss tangent. The loss tangent was then used to estimate the abundance of FeO and TiO₂. By combining the results of the permittivity and loss tangent, we conducted stratification and geological interpretation of the subsurface structures. For the low-frequency channel, we only analyzed signals within the 1,500 ns to 4,000 ns range to avoid the influence of strong system noise.

Results: The profiles of the high-frequency channel provide clear imaging of structures within a depth of over 40 m. A well-defined flat floor overlaying a recessive rebound zone can be observed in the radargram, which can readily be classified as a currently buried paleo flat-bottomed crater. Its morphology indicates that the impact reached the interface between the regolith and the substrate. The strength of the lower material is much greater than that of the upper material, allowing it to resist the deformation caused by the impact. Therefore, we hypothesize that the material at the bottom of the crater is a basalt unit, while the upper unit is a paleo-regolith layer.

By integrating the low-frequency and high-frequency data, along with impact crater statistics near the landing site, this study has identified at least four volcanic events with varying FeO and TiO₂ content in the Chang'e-4 landing area, dating back to the Nectarian period. During the Nectarian period, volcanic products were characterized by high titanium content, followed by medium titanium content in the Imbrian period. Over time, the thickness of the lava flow gradually decreased. Between the Nectarian and Imbrian basalt units, this study discovered two layers of material with extremely low FeO and TiO₂ content, likely ejecta from the Leibnitz and Schrödinger impact craters.

References:

- [1] W. Wu, C. Li, W. Zuo, et al. (2019) *Nat Geosci*, 12, 222. [2] Author A. B. and Author C. D. (1997) *JGR*, 90, 1151–1154. [2] C. Li, D. Liu, B. Liu, et al. (2019) *Nature*, 569, 378.

Fig. 1 Chang'e-4 landing site and the traversing path of Yutu-2 rover. (a) The location of South Pole-Aitken basin and Chang'e-4 mission landing site on the Moon. (b) Von Kármán Crater and vicinity area. The red star represents Chang'e-4 mission landing site. (c) The path of Yutu-2 rover during the 53 lunar days.